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Poverty in Agricultural labourers belong to downtrodden communities in India (Reference with Anantapur district in Andhra Pradesh State)

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Poverty in Agricultural labourers belong to downtrodden communities in India Reference with Anantapur district in Andhra Pradesh State 1. H. Sivasankar 2. Prof. G.VenkataNaidu 3. Dr. B.Ramachandra ABSTRACT The per capita income of some the agricultural labours are very low out of 100 of households and 456 individual there are 351 are poor.

ABSTRACT

The per capita income of some the agricultural labours are very low out of 100 of households and 456 individual there are 351 are poor. It seems to be more as it accounts for 76.97 per cent. Though the poor in study are more it severity of poverty not at the severe condition. The depth and severity are 0.011 and 0.003 respectively.

KEYWORDS

Downtrodden Communities, Agriculture labour, Poverty.

INTRODUCTION

Poverty is an everlasting problem in low income or developing countries. It not confined to the said countries it can be found the traces of poverty even in well developed countries. It seems to be economic problem, but it is multidimensional. It has become universal by virtue of multidimensional nature. To define poverty is not as easy as its pronunciation. By its multidimensional complexity it is defined in multi way. On economic grounds it is deprivation in per capita income to minimum standard of life or poverty line. UNO estimated world poverty that "close to 900 million people around the world live in severe poverty based on income poverty line of \$1.90 a day in 2015"¹. The World Bank estimated the world poverty. The Bank estimated that "today more than one billion people live on less than \$1 a day"². Further the report disclosed that

“around 70 per cent of those people are women, and almost half of the sub Saharan Africa population survives at that of income level”³. We know that a child dies at every 3.5 seconds in the developing world due to poverty conditions.

Ruddar Datt and Sundharam considered the measure of Poverty in India that accepted to identify the people as poor that “in India, general accepted definition of poverty emphasises minimum level of living rather than a reasonable level of living”⁴.

Poverty in other words deprivation is multi component and its wings are so lengthy that’s why deprivation has penetrated into various fields such as nutritious food, health, education etc in addition to per capita income. The pioneering work of ILO tried to redefine poverty in mid 1970s such that “not just as a failure to meet minimum nutrition or subsistence level, but rather as a failure to keep with the standards prevalent in given society”⁵.

The ILO reported that “working poverty has continued to decrease, but at slower rate than before the crisis. There are still 870 million workers are living with their families on less than US \$ 2 per person per day, of which nearly 400 million are living in extreme poverty. A further 660 million workers are living just above the poverty line and are at high risk of falling back”⁶.

As per the Global Multidimensional poverty Index, 41 per cent of people are living in multi dimensional poverty in South Asia. In Sub-Saharan it reached to 42 per cent in Europe and Central Asia multidimensional poverty registered 0.3 per cent. in East Asia and Pacific the Index is 8.8 per cent.

India has been encountering poverty since from past. The Global Multidimensional poverty Index 2020 pointed out “India’s rank is 62nd among 107 world countries 0.123 MPI score and 27.9 per cent of the people recognised as multi dimensionally poor”. Further the report specified that “the number (multi dimensionally poor) in rural India was 36.8 per cent and for urban it was 9.2”⁷.

Table No. 01: Poverty in India from 1973-74 to 2011-12

(In percentile)

Year	Rural	Urban	Total
1973-74	56.4	48.2	54.9
1977-78	53.1	47.4	51.8
1987-88	39.1	40.1	39.3
2004-05	41.8	25.7	37.2
2011-12	25.7	13.7	21.9

(Source: Compiled from Planning Commission (1993) and Economic Survey, GoI, 2013-14)

The poverty in India is obviously decreasing. The compiled data in the table is an evident for it. The percentage of poverty in rural India compare to urban is more. The rural poverty in the country in 2011-12 is just 50 percent compare to 1973-74, but below figure exposes that the decrement in population is not as same as the decrement prevailed in the table. The figure shows the rural people below poverty line in 1973-74 is 261.3 million whereas in 2011-12 it slides to 216.3 million. The table as well as the figure emphasis poverty particularly rural poverty should be taken in to account seriously.

Figure No.01: People in below poverty line in India
(In Millions)

(Source: Compiled from Planning Commission (1993) and Economic Survey, GoI, 2013-14)

Rural economy rests on agriculture. Poverty in agricultural sector will affect Indian economy along with rural people. The following figure shows poverty in agricultural labourer.

There is no doubt in gradual mitigation of poverty in agricultural labours in India. The figure reveals poverty level in 1993-94 was 70.4 percentile. Later on it fell to 63.1 per cent then it became 49.4 per cent and it reached to 39.8 percentile in 2011-12. The downwards linear trend line in the figure No.02 determines poverty in agricultural labours is diminishing. Ofcourse, diminishing trend is favour of the economy but, the important dimension that the suffering community should be hidden out to planning for lifting them from the whirlpool of poverty.

Figure No.02: Poverty in Agricultural Labours

(Source: poverty by social religious and economic groups in India & its largest states 1993-94 to 2011-12 by Aravind Panagariya, Columbia University working paper No.2013-02)

The naked truth in India that the down trodden communities such as SC and ST are living far away from the residence of upper communities for time immemorial with wealth less state. As said by United Nation Development Programme (UNDP), Oxford Poverty, Human Development Initiative (HDI) and Global Multidimensional Index 2018 “every second person belongs to ST and every third person belongs SC remains poor”. The percentage of poverty in SC and ST communities who are living in rural India was 53.5 in 2004-05. In 2011-12 it fell to 31.5 per cent.

The Times of India broken out that “in India five out of six multi dimensionally poor people are from lower Tribes or castes. The ST group accounts for 9.4 per cent of the population and is the poorest with 65 million of the 129 million people living in multi dimensional poverty. They account for one sixth of all people is living in multi dimensional poverty in India”⁸ and “overall five out of six multi dimensional poor people in India live in households whose heads is from SC, ST and other backward class”⁹. The survey originated that SCs/STs were a mere 25 per cent of the non-poor household”¹⁰. It does mean most of the people belong to the down trodden communities are living in multi dimensional poverty. The following table reveals community wise poverty in rural India.

Table No. 02: Poverty in different communities in rural India

Year	SC	ST	All
1993-94	62.4	65.9	50.1
2004-05	53.5	62.3	41.8
2011-12	31.5	45.3	25.7

(Source: The prin.com, 12th July, 2019)

The table makes to become clarify the poverty levels in different communities specifically down trodden communities. The percentage of Poor people prevailed in down trodden communities is more compare to overall percentage in give periods. Within the down trodden communities SCs are somewhat better than STs. We can find remarkable reduction in poverty i.e., around 50 per cent in SCs in the period from 1993-94 to 2011-12. In the same period the reduction in STs taken place from 65.9 to 45.3 per cent. In the same period overall poverty fell down from 50.1 to 25.7 per cent.

REVIEW LITERATURE

Surajith Deb opined that “low levels of income remains as the crucial reason for continuing of poverty in India”. Further he noted that though multi dimensional poverty index has indicated poverty reduction in large number in India during the period from 2005 to 2015-16, but large number of states across India remain vulnerable to caste based inequalities, this part of social change indicators series presents data on low income rural; households”¹¹.

Joseph E Stilglitz et al viewed poverty on inequalities grounds through the objective of economic development. The pointed out that “if economic growth is not contributed throughout the society development will be failed”¹².

Need of Study

Most of the labourers belong to down trodden communities are working in agricultural sector in Anantapur district. Famine is a permanent guest of the district. Many research works have been conducted in various fields in the district but no work has been conducted to estimate poverty and the impact of some determinants particularly income, employment, debt, expenditure on medical, literacy rate and family size on poverty on down trodden communities in the district.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the scenario of poverty in the study area
2. To study the impact of income levels, the employment levels, debt levels, family size, the literacy and the medical expenditure of respondents on poverty.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no poor respondent in the study area.
2. There is no change in poverty level due to a change in income, employment, debt, family size, literacy and medical expenditure

METHODOLOGY

Plan of study

Multi stage random sampling method is adopted. The district Anantapur is divided in to five revenue divisions. One mandal is randomly selected from each revenue division. From each mandal one village is randomly selected. Later, 100 samples from down trodden communities are randomly selected by blind fold method from five villages together.

Collection of data

The analysis is done an association with Primary as well as secondary data. The secondary data is collected from various sources and the primary data is collected by questionnaire and personal interviews. The secondary data is used for analysis in introduction part. The primary data is utilised in result and analysis part.

Result and Analysis

Poverty is not only subjective but objective also. It influences and it is influenced by many factors. It is a root cause for many problems. We can control many evil factors in the civic society by breaking the vicious circle of poverty. Hence, many economist and organisations focused attention on the subject matter of poverty. Ojha (1960-61), propose Rs.8-11 per capita consumption expenditure for rural population as poverty line for maintaining minimum level of nutrition. Dandekar and Rath fixed Rs.20 per month as poverty line. Minha, Bardhan, Montek Singh Ahluwalia etc conducted studies on poverty. Poverty can be estimated by the following methods.

Head count ratio (P_H):

Poor can be counted those whose income is below the poverty line. Hence, it can be expressed mathematically as.

$$P_H = \frac{q}{N} \quad \text{consider } y_i > z = 0, y_i < z$$

Hence,

$$q = \sum_{i=1}^n (q_i)$$

P_H = poverty head count ratio, y_i = per capita income, z = poverty line

Poverty gap Index (P_1)

The measure of head count ratio can reveal total persons whose per capita income below the poverty line but it does not refers gap between per capita income of individual and pervert line. Gauray Datt and Martin Ravallion, therefore, developed the concept of poverty gap. Foster Greer Thorbecke (FGT) developed poverty gap Index. Most of the economist considers it as a better one.

$$(P_{\alpha=1}) P_1 = \frac{1}{Nz} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^q (z - 1)$$

Poverty severity p_2 ($P_{\alpha=2}$)

It can be found by squaring or $\alpha=2$ which reveals the severity of poverty of the poor.

$$(P_{\alpha=2}) P_2 = 1/N(z)^2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^q (z - 2)$$

Poverty scenario in the study area

Head count ratio (P_H)	Poverty gap Index (P_1)	Poverty severity (P_2)
76.97%	0.011	0.003

Analysis impact of income, employment, debt, family size, medical expenditure and literacy on poverty:

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	366.369	6	61.062	230.647	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.621	93	.265		
	Total	390.990	99			
a. Dependent Variable: m						
b. Predictors: (Constant), VAR00006, VAR00005, VAR00002, VAR00003, VAR00004, VAR00001						

m = poverty, x₁ = income, x₂ = employment, x₃ = debt, x₄ = family size, x₅ = medical expenditure, x₆ = literacy

Above ANOVA Table confirms that the 'P' value of the total regression is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is significant. Therefore, the impact of income, employment, debt, family size, medical expenditure and literacy on poverty is true.

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
		1	(Constant)	10.336			.689	
	VAR00001	-.044	.011	-.379	-3.920	.000	-.067	-.022
	VAR00002	-.046	.003	-1.397	-16.145	.000	-.052	-.040
	VAR00003	-.004	.003	-.059	-1.380	.171	-.011	.002
	VAR00004	4.700	.151	1.969	31.045	.000	4.399	5.000
	VAR00005	-2.020	.120	-.583	-16.780	.000	-2.259	-1.781
	VAR00006	-.180	.087	-.076	-2.082	.040	-.352	-.008
a. Dependent Variable: m								

m = poverty, x₁ = income, x₂ = employment, x₃ = debt, x₄ = family size, x₅ = medical expenditure, x₆ = literacy

The co-efficient table ascertains that the impact of income, employment, medical expenditure and literacy except family size have negative correlation with poverty. It does mean the independent variable increases the dependent variable that is poverty will decrease. Another independent variable Debt is not significant. Therefore the variable need not to take into consideration as its 'P' value is more than 0.05. The table shows that there is positive correlation between family size and poverty.

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.968 ^a	.937	.933	.515	.937	230.647	6	93	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), VAR00006, VAR00005, VAR00002, VAR00003, VAR00004, VAR00001									

m = poverty, x₁ = income, x₂ = employment, x₃ = debt, x₄ = family size, x₅ = medical expenditure, x₆ = literacy

The table summarises that the regression line is fit for analysis as its R² value is 0.933. It does mean that the regression 93.3 per cent fit.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion derived from above analysis that the 351 poor agricultural labours in the total population 456 are there it account for 76.97 per cent in the study area but the depth is not at higher rate as per the analysis the depth is found as 0.011 and the severity is 0.003. Therefore the poverty conditions are not at severe.

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